

Effect of Extreme Photoperiodic Condition-constant Light and Melatonin Pretreatment on Ampicillin Induced Nephrotoxicity in Wild Tropical Rodent, Indian palm squirrel, *F. pennanti*.

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Running Title: Nephrotoxicity by Ampicilline sodium

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Introduction:

Melatonin is the main product synthesized by the vertebrate pineal gland. This substance is ubiquitous in species from protozoa to mammals including human beings. In photoperiodic mammals, melatonin is probably best known for its effects on seasonal reproductive physiology (Haldar, 1997; Reiter, 1993; Gerlach and Aurich, 2000), circadian rhythmicity (Armstrong, 1989) and immune function (Maestroni, 1993). In humans it has been tested most frequently for its ability to reduce the symptoms of jet lag (Arendt et al., 1996), to adjust to 24-h rhythmicity, and as a sleep aid, (Dawson and Encel, 1993). Its synthesis is rhythmic with high melatonin level occurring at night and low levels during the day. It is known that melatonin acts as a free radical scavenger and as an antioxidant (Sharma et al., 2008; Hardeland et al., 1993; Qi et al., 1999). Oxygen free radicals are continually produced in tissues of aerobic organisms. Excessive production of these radicals and especially hydroxyl (OH•) radicals leads to indiscriminate damage to macromolecules including DNA, proteins and membrane phospholipids. To resist this damage, organisms are equipped with a number of agents; these include vitamin E, vitamin C, uric acid, reduced glutathione (GSH) and enzymes such as superoxide dismutase (SOD).

On the other hand, it is evident that oxidative stress is involved in the pathophysiology of renal disease; Deman et al. (2001) showed antibiotics induced decrease of antioxidant enzymes (catalase and superoxide dismutase) in renal tissue. Many studies have provided evidences for the beneficial effect and protective role of antioxidants in the pathologies (Sechi et al., 1997; Mimic-Oka et al., 1999). Specifically, melatonin having research evidences carried out by our group reduced significantly the intensity of oxidative stress induced by radiation (Sharma et al., 2008), hyperlipidemia and signs of renal disruption induced in rats by antibiotics (Montilla et al., 1997, 1998). Such effects were reduced when melatonin was used against gentamicin toxicity (Ozbek et al., 2000). Peripheral melatonin level can be induced noninvasively by photoperiodic exposures. Long days inhibit melatonin synthesis while short day stimulates. Constant light performs physiological pinealectomy while constant dark induces basal level but makes the melatonin rhythm free running.

Considering these data in relation to melatonin and antioxidant systems in kidney, (Pierrefiche and Laborit, 1995) our main aim was to evaluate the effects of melatonin and constant light exposure which functions as physiological pinealectomy and extremely reduce the melatonin level on antioxidant enzyme activities in renal tissue (TAS%, SOD), oxidative stress lipid peroxidation level (TBARS) in nephropathy induced by Ampicillin

Experimental setup:

Thirty five (35) adult male squirrels (weighing 100g to 120g each) were used in this study. The squirrels were collected from the vicinity of the Varanasi (Lat. 25°18'N; Long. 83°01'E) and acclimatized for one weeks in a room fully exposed to ambient environmental conditions (Light 12.50 hr; Temp. 20–25°C; Humidity, 29–50%). The animals were housed in wire net cages (25" X 75" X 30") and had an access to food consisting of soaked gram seeds (*Cicer arietinum*) and water ad libitum. Later, the Squirrels were divided into five groups of 7 animals each,

Group-I Control.

Seven male squirrels were kept in natural environmental condition as mentioned above without any treatment (NDL).

Group-II Continuous light Control (LL; 24 h light: 0h dark).

Seven male squirrels were kept under constant light conditions (LL).

Group-III Continuous light (LL; 24 h light: 0h dark) with Melatonin.

Seven male squirrels were kept under constant light conditions (LL) and received subcutaneously high doses of Melatonin (500µg/kg body weight/day) every evening hour between 5:30 to 6:30 pm, prepared fresh every day (LL+Mel).

Group-IV Continuous light (LL; 24 h light: 0h dark) with Ampicillin Sodium.

Seven male squirrels were kept under constant light conditions (LL), with single dose of Ampicillin sodium injected intra-muscularly (40mg/Kg body weight/ day) every morning between 10am to 10:30am, reconstituted fresh every day (LL+Amp).

Group-V Continuous light (LL; 24 h light: 0h dark) with Ampicillin and Melatonin.

Seven male squirrels were kept under constant light condition (LL), treated with intra-muscular dose of Ampicillin sodium (40mg/Kg body weight/day) every morning between 10am to 10:30am, reconstituted fresh every day and received subcutaneously high doses of Melatonin (500µg/kg body weight/day) every evening hour between 5:30 to 6:30 pm, prepared fresh every day (LL+Amp+Mel) day before Ampicillin treatment.

Methods and Parameters Assayed:

All the treatments were given for seven days and on the eighth day that is after 24 hours of last treatments animals were decapitated. The bladder was surgically extruded and emptied by supra-pubic puncture. This procedure ensured collection of urine produced over a period of 60 min. At the time of sacrifice, urine was collected and its volume was measured and biochemical parameters ACP, ALP, Creatinine and Urea were estimated. After removal of both kidneys through a midline abdominal incision, the right and left kidneys were processed. The kidneys were stripped from their capsule, weighed, and slit by longitudinal incision. Cortical, medullary (outer medulla), and papillary (inner medulla-papillary tip) components were separated under a dissecting microscope. Kidney tissues were also fixed in Bouin's fluid for histology. The accuracy of the dissection was verified by light microscopy.

Renal cortical tissue homogenates were prepared separately (as mentioned in materials and methods) for the detection of Superoxide dismutase activity (SOD), lipid peroxidation level (TBARS), Total antioxidative status (TAS %) and total kidney cortical protein. Trunk Blood was collected in separate centrifuge tubes and blood was taken for biochemical estimations that are ACP, ALP, urea and creatinine.

Histology:

After fixation in Bouin's fluid for 22 hours, kidney was paraffin embedded and cut into 6- μ m sections. Deparaffinized sections were stained using hematoxylin and eosin. Kidney morphology was observed under microscope (Leica MPV-3, Germany). The morphometric analysis of capsular space and cellular integrity (PCT, DCT & glomerulus) of kidney cortical region were done in 20 serial sections randomly selected from each animal with the help of filar ocular micrometer (Webcon Pvt. Ltd. India)

Statistical analysis:

All the data were expressed as means \pm SEM of at least seven animals per group. Data comparisons were statistically analyzed by using ANOVA followed by Student Newman-Keuls' multiple range tests. The differences were considered statistically significant when $p < 0.05$ (Bruning and Knitz, 1977). Microsoft Excel program was used for statistical calculations, plotting and illustration.

Results:

Fig. 1

Effect of melatonin pretreatment (500 μ g/Kg body wt) under constant light (LL) condition on Acid phosphatase (ACP) in (A) blood, (B) urine and alkaline phosphatase (ALP) in (C) blood, (D) of *F. pennanti*. Histogram represent Mean + SEM, (N=7); Vertical bar on each histogram represent standard error of mean. Significance of difference * $p < 0.05$ and ** $p < 0.001$. Control (Control) vs Constant light (LL), Constant light + Ampicillin treated (LL + Amp), Constant light + Melatonin treated (LL + mel) and Constant light + Melatonin + Ampicillin treated (LL + mel + ampi) groups.

Fig. 2

Effect of melatonin pretreatment (500 μ g/Kg body wt) under constant light (LL) condition on blood urea nitrogen (BUN) (A), urine urea (B) and creatinine in blood (C) urine (D) of *F. pennanti*. Histogram represent Mean + SEM, (N=7); Vertical bar on each histogram represent standard error of mean. Significance of difference * $p < 0.05$ and ** $p < 0.001$. Control (Control) vs Constant light (LL), Constant light + Ampicillin treated (LL + Amp), Constant light + Melatonin treated (LL + mel) and Constant light + Melatonin + Ampicillin treated (LL + mel + ampi) groups.

Fig.3

(A) Effect of melatonin pretreatment (500µg/Kg body wt) under constant light (LL) condition on the malon-dialdehyde level (TBARS) of *F. pennanti*. Histogram represent Mean + SEM, (N=7); Vertical bar on each histogram represent standard error of mean. Significance of difference * p<0.05 and ** p<0.001. Control (Control) vs Constant light (LL), Constant light + Ampicillin treated (LL + Amp), Constant light + Melatonin treated (LL + mel) and Constant light + Melatonin + Ampicillin treated (LL + mel + ampi) groups.

(B) Effect of melatonin pretreatment (500µg/Kg body wt) under constant light (LL) condition on the total kidney cortical protein weight of *F. pennanti*. Histogram represent Mean + SEM, (N=7); Vertical bar on each histogram represent standard error of mean. Significance of difference * p<0.05 and ** p<0.001. Control (Control) vs Constant light (LL), Constant light + Ampicillin treated (LL + Amp), Constant light + Melatonin treated (LL + mel) and Constant light + Melatonin + Ampicillin treated (LL + mel + ampi) groups.

(C) Effect of melatonin pretreatment (500µg/Kg body wt) under constant light (LL) condition on super oxide-dismutase activity (SOD) of *F. pennanti*. Histogram represent Mean + SEM, (N=7); Vertical bar on each histogram represent standard error of mean. Significance of difference * p<0.05 and ** p<0.001. Control (Control) vs Constant light (LL), Constant light + Ampicillin treated (LL + Amp), Constant light + Melatonin treated (LL + mel) and Constant light + Melatonin + Ampicillin treated (LL + mel + ampi) groups.

(D) Effect of melatonin pretreatment (500µg/Kg body wt) under constant light (LL) condition on the total antioxidative status (TAS %) of *F. pennanti*. Histogram represent Mean + SEM, (N=7); Vertical bar on each histogram represent standard error of mean. Significance of

difference * $p < 0.05$ and ** $p < 0.001$. Control (Control) vs Constant light (LL), Constant light + Ampicillin treated (LL + Amp), Constant light + Melatonin treated (LL + mel) and Constant light + Melatonin + Ampicillin treated (LL + mel + ampi) groups.

Fig. 3
Plate 1

Histomicrograph of squirrel kidney cortical region showing Glomerular (G), increased capsular space (\rightarrow), affected brush bordered vesicular epithelial cells (BBVEC) (*) of proximal convoluted tubule (PCT), distal convoluted tubule (DCT), loop of henle and collecting tubule. (Under 40X objective)

- A-** Control (Control)
- B-** Constant light (LL)
- C-** Constant light + Ampicillin treated (LL + Amp)
- D-** Constant light + Melatonin treated (LL + mel)
- E-** Constant light + Melatonin + Ampicillin treated (LL + mel + ampi)

Exposure of squirrels, to constant light with nephropathy induced by ampicillin, led to a significant ($p < 0.01$) increase in TBARS level (Fig.3), while total kidney cortical protein and TAS% decreased significantly ($p < 0.01$). Continuous light with ampicillin increased acid phosphatase and urea significantly ($p < 0.01$) in blood and urine (Fig.1 & 2). There was significant ($p < 0.01$) increase in SOD activity but a decrease in TAS% in (LL) groups when compared to control group. Administration of exogenous high doses of melatonin (LL) and Ampicillin treated groups under (LL) caused drop in lipid peroxidation level (TBARS) formation. Treatment with melatonin, in addition decreased formation of free radicals, prompted an increase of total antioxidative status in both the ampicillin group and the groups

exposed to constant light (LL) but less than control groups. This considerable improvement in oxidative stress marker values following administration of melatonin to animals with nephropathy was supported by the histological observations. The biochemical changes induced by Ampicillin in the levels of ACP, ALP, Creatinine and urea (Fig. 3) were restored by melatonin pretreatment.

Histological observation showed significant ($p < 0.01$) decrease in capsular space under constant light (LL), ampicillin treatment and melatonin pretreated ampicillin groups when compared with control squirrels. Melatonin alone under LL had no significant change in capsular space and cellular integrity. The cellular integrity of proximal convoluted tubular cells (PCT) was not observed in all experimental groups under LL condition (Plate1& Table1).

**MEASUREMENT OF CAPSULAR SPACE (CS) OF
 BOWMAN'S CAPSULE AND LUMINAL SPACE OF PCT
 (20 SECTIONS/GROUP)**

Treatments	Capsular Space (CS) of Bowman's cup	Luminal space of PCT
Control	10.42 ± 0.12 µm	14.28 ± 0.29 µm
Continuous Light (LL)	4.62 ± 0.44** µm	07.28 ± 0.58** µm
Continuous Light (LL)+ Melatonin (500 µg/kg body wt. SC in evening hours 1-130 µm)	6.14 ± 0.84 µm	08.62 ± 0.44** µm
Continuous Light (LL)+ Ampicillin sodium (40mg/kg body wt. i.v. in morning hours 11-13 am)	0.12 ± 0.16** µm	01.28 ± 0.33** µm
Continuous Light (LL) + Melatonin + Ampicillin sodium (500 µg/kg body wt. SC in evening hours 5-530 µm over day prior to the Ampicillin)	3.98 ± 0.12** µm	09.28 ± 0.63** µm

Capsular space (CS) = Bowman's capsule – Glomerular capillaries diameter. Significance of difference ** $p < 0.01$; Control vs Experimental groups.

Table 1

Discussion:

The results obtained here demonstrated an increase in oxidative stress in experimental nephropathy induced by Ampicillin under constant light exposure. This oxidative imbalance was evident not only in increased lipid peroxidation level (TBARS) with respect to the control and ampicillin group, but also in an overall impairment in antioxidant enzyme status (TAS%) which underwent a significant drop. Previous studies have shown that the animals exposed to constant light display elevated lipid peroxidation levels in brain, liver and kidney, (Baydas et al., 2001) suggesting a generalized increase in free radical production accompanying exposure to light. Secretion of melatonin by the pineal gland displays a circadian rhythm; thus, both synthesis and release of melatonin are stimulated by darkness and inhibited by light. Inhibition of melatonin synthesis by constant light exposure (LL), evident here by a drop in serum and renal tissue levels, may also account for the worsening of the already impaired oxidative balance found in rats with nephropathy induced by Ampicillin.

In our study, there was a fall in levels of kidney cortical protein when nephropathic animals were exposed to constant light, probably due to both the effects of constant light and the depletion generated by oxidative stress after ampicillin administration. There was also a drop in antioxidant enzyme activities under constant light. Similar findings were also reported recently for other experimental models, which revealed a decline in SOD activity, GPx activity and other enzymes in different tissues of animals exposed to constant light. (Pablos et al, 1995; Baydas et al., 2001; Albarran et al., 2001) However, the already marked deterioration recorded here in antioxidant enzyme activity due to nephropathy induced by Ampicillin, was not a factor recorded in Pablos's study (1995) Albaran's (2001) or Baydas's study (2001). In order to limit oxidative damage in nephropathy induced by Ampicillin, aggravated by (LL), animals received exogenous melatonin. Although endogenous melatonin was inhibited by constant exposure to light, administration of melatonin at pharmacological levels prompted significantly raised plasma and renal tissue melatonin levels, decreased free radicals and the activity of the antioxidant enzymes, thus limiting oxidative damage to the kidney. Melatonin is well known to prevent oxidative damage to polyunsaturated fatty acids in the cell membrane and to prevent damage to organelles and to nuclear and mitochondrial DNA by donating electrons as a mechanism of action (Reiter et al., 2000). In addition, melatonin stimulates the synthesis of antioxidant enzymes, mainly glutathione peroxidase and glutathione reductase (Deman et al., 2001), suggesting that melatonin may act not only directly against free radicals, but also indirectly as a stimulator of enzyme production, although the specific induction mechanism is unknown. (Albarran et al., 2001) In previous studies, authors found melatonin to be more effective as an antioxidant in experimental nephropathy induced by antibiotics than vitamin E (Mimic-Oka et al., 1999). This may be due to its wide cellular distribution, since it crosses all morpho-physiological barriers (Reiter et al., 2000). Previous studies have shown the melatonin lowered lipid peroxidation levels and increased reduced glutathione concentrations both in plasma and in the kidney in experimental nephropathy induced by Adriamycin, (Montilla et al., 1997, 1998) findings confirmed by the present study. We have also shown that melatonin is able not only to limit oxidative damage to the kidney during nephropathy induced by ampicillin, but can also improve oxidative stress in experimental nephropathy induced by Adriamycin (Montilla et al., 1997).

Hypothetical diagram showing the effect of Constant Light (LL) in Ampicillin induced nephrotoxicity in *F. pennanti*

In conclusion, the results obtained here suggest that an increase in oxidative stress occurs in animals with or without experimentally induced nephropathy when exposed to constant light; the increase is reversed by administration of exogenous melatonin. Finally, it should be mentioned that the potent protective effect of melatonin, due to its possible clinical utility, may provide a basis for new developments in renal pathology.

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